

SOP: Determining Protein Carbonylation

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Principle

The formation of oxygen-derived free radicals has been frequently detected for several nanomaterials (NMs) *in vitro* and *in vivo*. Proteins are one of the major targets of oxygen free radicals and other reactive species leading to oxidative protein modification. The formation of protein carbonyls is one of the major modifications. Protein carbonylation has already been detected after NM treatment (e.g. Driessen et al. 2015).

The carbonyl groups in the protein side chains are derivatized to 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone (DNP-hydrazone) by reaction with 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine (DNPH).

Figure 1: Protein carbonyl groups are derivatized with 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine (DNPH) to the respective DNP-hydrazone

The DNP-derivatized proteins can be then separated by SDS- polyacrylamide gel electrophoresis followed by immunoblotting, or directly dotted on a blot membrane. Signals are detected using a DNP antibody and chemiluminescence (ECL). Signals from NM treated samples are compared to signals from untreated control samples.

1.2. Application area

The assay can indirectly determine the oxidative stress potential of NMs by measuring one (major) type of oxidative protein modification. In contrast to dye-based assays that directly measure the formation of the oxygen radicals there are no interferences of NMs with the read-out principle here. Thus, the assay is useful for all types of NMs (e.g. metals, metal oxides, carbon-based, polymeric NMs). For the analysis protein containing lysates are used (e.g. total cell extracts). Therefore

samples from *in vitro* studies (cell lysates) can be analysed as well as samples from *in vivo* studies (lysates from different organs). This assay is very sensitive and (according to the manufacturer) can detect as little as 5 femtomoles of carbonyl residues.

1.3. Safety measures

In-house procedures for safe handling of NMs and other potentially hazardous compounds should be followed. Cell culture work should be performed in a laminar flow Biosafety cabinet to ensure sterile handling of cell cultures.

2. EQUIPMENT AND REAGENTS

2.1. Reagents for cell culture

- NRK-52E cells, DMSZ, ACC 199
- complete cell medium (DMEM (high Glucose), PAN Biotech P04-01161; 10 % Filtrated bovine serum (FBS) not heat-inactivated, Good PAN Biotech, P40-37500; 2 mM L-Glutamin; 100 U/ml (0,1 mg/ml) Penicillin / Streptomycin; 25 mM Hepes Puffer)

2.2. Reagents

- modified RIPA-Buffer for cell lysis (50 mM Tris/HCl pH 7.4, 150 mM NaCl, 1 mM EDTA, 1 % Igepal, 0.25 % Na-deoxycholate)
- protease inhibitors (Protease Inhibitor Cocktail Set III, Millipore, Germany)
- 2-mercaptoethanol
- reagents for protein quantification, Bradford assay (BioRad)
- bovine serum albumin as a standard for protein quantification
- Millipore Oxiblot® kit (Millipore, Germany, S7150)
- 12% (w/v) sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) solution in dH₂O
- 72% (w/v) trichloroacetic acid solution (TCA) in dH₂O
- pre-cooled acetone (-20°C)
- 1 M Tris Base (not pH adjusted)
- reagents for SDS protein gel electrophoresis (10% gels, minigel format) using Laemmli sample buffer
- reagents for immunoblotting (e.g. TBST, nitrocellulose membrane)
- Rotiblock® (Carl-Roth, Germany),

- tubulin antibody for loading control (anti-alpha Tubulin from chicken, Abcam, ab89984) and anti-chicken secondary antibody (Goat anti-chicken IgY H&L (HRP), Abcam, ab97135)
- Colloidal Gold Total Protein Stain (BioRad, 1706527)
- reagents for chemiluminescence detection (ECL), e.g. SuperSignal West Pico ECL (Pierce/ Thermo Scientific)

2.3. Equipment

- equipment for dispersing NMs (here: Cup Horn ultrasonication)
- equipment for cell culture (e.g. laminar flow hood, cell incubator)
- equipment for SDS protein gel electrophoresis (e.g. BioRad, mingel format)
- equipment for immunoblotting (e.g. semi-dry transfer system)
- equipment for ECL detection

3. SOLUTIONS

3.1. Carbonyl Immunoblot

The kit contains the following solutions:

- 2,4-Dinitrophenylhydrazine (DNPH) Solution
- Neutralization Solution
- Primary Antibody: Rabbit Anti-DNP Antibody
- Secondary Antibody: Goat Anti-Rabbit IgG (HRP-conjugated)

3.2. Test items

3.2.1. Preparation of NP dispersions

NPs are dispersed using the NanoToxClass or the Nanogenotox dispersion SOP. Briefly, in the NanoToxClass dispersion protocol a defined amount of NMS (here between 0.5 and 1 mg) is weighed in a 2 mL plastic centrifuge tube. Each tube is filled up to a concentration of 0.5 mg/ml with cell culture medium without fetal calf serum (FCS). The tubes are placed in the Cup Horn and the suspension is sonicated with a final effective sonication power of 6 W (for Bandelin UW 2200, this power is reached by 100% duty cycle, 100% power for 23 minutes). The suspensions are diluted to the desired final concentration with cell culture medium supplemented with FCS and then the suspensions are stirred for minimum 10 minutes (up to 1h).

3.2.2. Cell treatment & Cell lysates

Cells are seeded in 6-well plates 24h before the treatment, so that just before the treatment the cells are 85% confluent. The exact number of cells seeded has to be adjusted in each laboratory; at BfR this confluence could be obtained when ca.

0.17×10^6 NRK-52E cells pro well (1.8×10^4 cell/cm²) and 0.23×10^6 A549 cells pro well (2.5×10^4 cell/cm²) are seeded. After 24h rest the cell culture medium is removed and replaced with 3 mL cell culture medium containing the desired final NM concentration (i.e. 0, 10, 25, 50 µg/mL which corresponds respectively to 3.3, 8.3 and 16.6 µg/mL). Cells are treated for 6h. After treatment the cell culture medium is removed, the cell culture dish is placed on ice and cells are washed three times with ice-cold PBS (without Ca²⁺/Mg²⁺). Lysis buffer is added and cells are lysed in a modified RIPA-Buffer containing protease inhibitors and 2-mercaptoethanol (1 % v/v). Cells can be either detached in the lysis buffer using a pipette, i.e. rinsing off the cells or can be scraped off using a cell scraper. Crude lysates are transferred into new plastic tubes (1.5 mL) and incubated for 30 minutes on ice with occasional vortexing every 5 min (alternatively tubes can be placed on a rotator for 30 min in a cold room). Samples are then centrifuged (4 °C, 17000 × g, 15 min) and the supernatants (= cell lysates) are transferred into fresh plastic tubes. Protein concentrations are determined using Bradford assay according to manufacturer instructions with bovine serum albumin (BSA) as a standard (BSA concentrations: 0 - 25 µg/mL). In order to exclude any possible interference of the lysis-buffer with the assay, the lysates were diluted 1:200 in milliQ water before determining the protein concentration (the comparison between the BSA standard curve recorded in lysis-buffer diluted 1:200 in milliQ water and the same curve recorded in milliQ water showed no meaningful difference, especially in the range of concentration of our cell lysates).

4. EXPERIMENTAL PROTOCOL

4.1. Coupling to DNP-hydrazine

Protein carbonyls are detected using the Millipore Oxiblot® kit (Millipore, Germany) according to manufacturer instructions. For SDS-Page and Immunoblot preferably 20-25 µg protein are used, lower amounts may also be used but amount should not be less than 10 µg. For Dot Blot 5 µg protein are used and the volumes of the reagents are reduced accordingly.

In brief:

- Use 20- 25 µg protein lysates in 20 µl (fill up to 20 µl)
- Add 20 µl 12 % SDS-Lösung
- Add 40 µl DNPH-Lösung (contained in Oxyblot kit)
- Incubate 15 min at 24° C inkubiert
- Add 30 µl neutralization solution (contained in Oxyblot kit)

Then proteins are precipitated using 15 µl TCA (final concentration approx. 10%). For precipitation of proteins incubate after adding TCA for 30 min on ice followed by 25 min centrifugation (18000x g, 4 °C). Discard the supernatant, wash pellet with 700 µl Aceton (-20°C), centrifuge again, wash again with 80% Aceton/ 20% dH₂O,

centrifuge again. Discard the supernatant and dry the pellet (e.g. 15 min in a concentrator or air-dry). For SDS-PAGE and Immunoblot add 10 μ l Laemmli buffer to dissolve the pellet- this may be enhanced by placing samples in ultrasonication bath (5 min). If Laemmli buffer turns yellow add droplet wise (1 μ L each) 1M Tris Base (not pH adjusted). For Dot Blot add 4 μ l TBST to dissolve the pellet- this may be enhanced by placing samples in ultrasonication bath (5 min).

4.2. SDS-PAGE and Immunoblot

After coupling proteins are separated using a 10 % SDS-PAGE. Proteins are transferred to nitrocellulose membranes using a semi-dry transfer system (200 mA/Gel, 1 h). Membranes are blocked with Rotiblock, washed three times for 10 minutes using TBST, and incubated with primary antibodies (contained in Oxyblot kit), diluted 1:150 in TBST, overnight at 4 °C or 1 h at room temperature. Membranes are then washed three times for 10 minutes using TBST, incubated with secondary antibody (contained in Oxyblot kit), diluted 1:300 in TBST for 1 h at room temperature, washed again 3 times for 10 minutes with TBST and visualized using ECL. Chemiluminescence is detected using a GelDoc system.

For normalization the tubulin signal of the same membrane is used. Before doing so, the membrane should be dried completely (preferably for 2-3 days) to eliminate the signal from DNP antibodies. Stripping is not a good alternative here. Tubulin antibody is used in a 1:5000 dilution in TBST. After 2-3 h incubation at room temperature membranes are washed three times using TBST, then incubated with goat anti-chicken (1:10000 in TBST) for 1 h at room temperature, washed again three times with TBST and visualized using ECL.

4.3. Dot Blot

1 μ L of protein solution (from paragraph 4.1) is deposited onto nitrocellulose membranes in triplicates and let dry for 15 minutes. Membranes are blocked with Rotiblock, washed three times for 5 minutes using TBST, and incubated with primary antibodies (contained in Oxyblot kit), diluted 1:150 in TBST, overnight at 4 °C or 1 h at room temperature. Membranes are then washed three times for 5 minutes using TBST, incubated with secondary antibody (contained in Oxyblot kit), diluted 1:300 in TBST for 30 minutes at room temperature, washed again 3 times for 5 minutes with TBST and visualized using ECL. Chemiluminescence is detected using a GelDoc system.

For normalization the total amount of protein bound to the nitrocellulose membranes was identified by Colloidal Gold Total Protein Stain from Bio-Rad according to manufacturer instructions. Before doing so, the membrane should be dried

completely (preferably for 2-3 days) to eliminate the signal from DNP antibodies. Stripping is not a good alternative here.

5. DATA Evaluation

Signals obtained with DNP antibody are compared for NM treated samples to control samples, (i.e. untreated cells) taking into account equal loading using tubulin signal (Immunoblot) or total protein stain (Dot Blot). In case of Immunoblot densitometric analysis (e.g. using ImageLab, BioRad or similar software) is possible but not straightforward as the DNP signal is not a single band or a couple of single bands but rather occurs as a “smear” over a broad size range. Thus, typically expert judgement is performed only to classify responses as strong/ medium/ low or as negative compared to untreated controls. In case of Dot Blot densitometric analysis is performed.

6. Acceptance criteria

7. Literature

Oxyblot Kit manufacturer instruction

Driessen et al. 2015 Proteomic analysis of protein carbonylation: a useful tool to unravel nanoparticle toxicity mechanisms *Particle and Fibre Toxicology* 12:36
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